

United States Department of the Interior

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE
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In reply refer to:
08FBDT00-2019-F-0056

July 6, 2020

Ms. Andrea Meier
Acting Chief
North Branch Regulatory Division
U.S. Department of the Army
Corps of Engineers
San Francisco District
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San Francisco, California 94102-3406

Subject: Formal Consultation on the Marin County Department of Public Works North San Pedro Road Culvert Rehabilitation Project, China Camp State Park, San Rafael, Marin County, California (U.S. Army Corps of Engineers File Number: 2017-00537N)

Dear Ms. Meier:

This letter is in response to the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers' (Corps') November 26, 2018, request to initiate consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) for the Marin County Department of Public Works' (Applicant) North San Pedro Road Culvert Rehabilitation Project (Project) in the City of San Rafael in Marin County, California. Your request was received by the Service on November 30, 2018. At issue are the proposed Project's effects to the federally-threatened California red-legged frog (*Rana draytonii*), the endangered salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*), and the endangered California clapper rail (*Rallus obsoletus obsoletus*)¹. This response is provided under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*) (Act), and in accordance with the implementing regulations pertaining to interagency cooperation (50 CFR § 402).

The Federal action on which we are consulting is the Corps' issuance of a permit under Section

¹ Until the Service officially adopts recent nomenclature changes made by the American Ornithologists' Union to Ridgway's Rail (*Rallus obsoletus*), we maintain the use of California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*) in this correspondence. Note, the change in taxonomic assignment does not change the listing status of the species.

404 of the Clean Water Act of 1972, as amended (33 U.S.C. § 1344 *et seq.*), and Section 10 of the Rivers and Harbors Act of 1899, as amended (33 U.S.C. § 403 *et seq.*), allowing the Applicant to repair six culverts and the adjacent road shoulder on North San Pedro Road. This will allow flow of waters from the tidal marsh on the east side of the road to the muted tidal marshes on the west side of the road, as well as allow outflow of downstream run off from the creeks and surrounding hills into San Pablo Bay. Pursuant to 50 CFR § 402.12(j), you submitted a biological assessment for our review and requested concurrence with the findings presented therein.

In considering your request, we have based our evaluation on the following: (1) the Corps' November 26, 2018, letter requesting informal consultation; (2) the Applicant's June 2019 *Section 7 Biological Assessment: North San Pedro Culvert Rehabilitation Project - San Rafael, Marin County, California* (BA), prepared by WRA Environmental Consultants; (3) electronic mail (email) correspondence between the Service, the Corps, and the Applicant, exchanged from December 20, 2018 to January 27, 2020, concerning responses to the Service's requests for additional information; (4) the Corps' July 19, 2019, email containing a revised request to initiate formal consultation; (5) the Applicant's August 27, 2019, letter to the Service responding to a request for clarification on Project effects to species; and (6) other information available to the Service.

The Service concurs with the Corps' determination that the proposed Project may affect, but is not likely to adversely affect the threatened California red-legged frog, based on: (1) the unlikelihood of California red-legged frog presence within the Action Area given occurrence records nearest the Project site are in an independent watershed with major dispersal barriers present; (2) the Action Area only contains 24 linear feet of creek that constitutes marginal breeding habitat given it is subject to considerable brackish tidal influence and doesn't feature any deep pools; (3) waters within the Project footprint are characterized by salinity gradients outside of the physiological optima for the species; (4) screened pumps will be utilized during dewatering activities; and (5) the implementation of the *Conservation Measures* detailed within the *Description of the Proposed Action* section below which include provisions for halting work and contacting the Service for further recommendations if any individuals are observed.

The Service could not concur with the Corps' determination that the proposed Project may affect, but is not likely to adversely affect the threatened California clapper rail, based on the potential effects to individuals and temporary habitat loss expected from Project implementation as proposed by the Applicant.

Per the Corps' July 19, 2019, email requesting initiation of formal consultation, and after review of the Applicant's, August 27, 2019, response letter to the Service, the remainder of this document provides our biological opinion on the effects of the proposed Project on the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail.

Consultation History

November 30, 2018 The San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office received the Corps' consultation initiation request letter for concurrence with the not likely to

	adversely affect determinations for the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse.
December 2018— March 2019	The Service requested an effects analysis be included in a BA, and provided technical assistance to the Corps and Applicant regarding the prudence of the Corps consulting informally or formally on the proposed Project.
July 18, 2019	The Corps submitted the Applicant's BA and notified the Service their Project determination for salt marsh harvest mouse had changed to may affect, and is likely to adversely affect, following further consideration of the proposed activities potential effects. The Corps subsequently requested initiation of formal consultation with the Service. The BA also concluded that the project may affect, but is not likely to adversely affect the California red-legged frog and California clapper rail.
July 2019— August 2019	The Service requested clarification on the likelihood of California clapper rail and California red-legged frog presence in the area during project implementation.
August 27, 2019	The Applicant responded to the Service's request and submitted a BA revision that described and quantified potential effects to the California clapper rail.
September 2019— December 2019	The Service requested additional information regarding the results of the area of habitat affected for each species, and the timeline and duration expected for implementation of the proposed Project.
February 7, 2020	The Service deems the consultation initiation package to be complete and initiated formal section 7 consultation for the Project.

BIOLOGICAL OPINION

Description of the Proposed Action

The Applicant proposes to repair six (6) culverts and the adjacent road shoulder on North San Pedro Road at mile markers 3.2, 3.27, 3.39, 3.78, 3.81 and 3.84 in Marin, California (see Figure 1). These allow flow of waters from the tidal marsh on the east side of the road to the muted tidal marshes on the west side of the road, as well as allow outflow of downstream run off from the creeks and surrounding hills into San Pablo Bay. The Applicant is required to maintain North San Pedro Road for public access and safety and the six culverts are in poor condition. Work to rehabilitate the culverts is necessary to limit further damage and restore essential function to the culverts and to support the road. All culverts are corrugated metal pipe (CMP) which has degraded.

All culverts will be vactored to remove sediment. Some of the culvert ends will be trimmed and in some cases new CMP will be placed to restore and extend to their original length. After the culverts have been cleaned and repaired, they will be slip-lined with polyvinyl chloride (PVC) material, supported and protected by native soil and rock, and then backfilled to recreate the road shoulder. Native compactable soil will be used to backfill over the culverts and to re-create missing dirt road shoulders. Soil will be compacted to support the culverts and to close any air gaps.

A low-impact PVC material will be used to rehabilitate the culverts. The chosen vendor uses a manufacturing process for the PVC liner that is completed at the factory and circumvents bringing hazardous water-soluble chemicals to the jobsite which could leak from the process into the ground water or streams. Consequently, no noxious off-gassing will pollute the air and create olfactory disturbance to resident populations of human and wildlife species. The PVC material will be heated in the truck, then pulled through the culvert. The material will undergo steam pressure to expand it into the CMP. Any remaining annular gaps at the openings (1 inch or less) will be grouted. Stabilizers are not necessary and will not be used.

Any rock in the channel from fallen headwalls will be collected for re-use. Each day, temporary coffer dams will be installed. The coffer dams will consist of 0.6 cubic yard bags (4 feet x 4 feet x 1 foot high) of clean gravel which will be placed in the channel. The work site will be dewatered with two-inch trash pumps, and the water will be allowed to filter back into the marsh.

Headwalls to protect the culverts and to protect the road bank from scour (except for the existing concrete headwalls at mile markers 3.27 and 3.78 inlets) will be constructed of rock pressed into the compacted soil. The size of the rock will vary between 18-inch on the bottom to 6-inch at the

Figure 1. Map of mile markers where culvert repair will take place on North San Pedro Road as part of the Marin County Department of Public Works North San Pedro Road Culvert Rehabilitation Project. Adapted from *Section 7 Biological Assessment: North San Pedro Culvert Rehabilitation Project - San Rafael, Marin County, California* (WRA Environmental Consultants 2019).

top of the walls. The two existing concrete headwalls are in good condition and the Applicant expects them to last a significant amount of time into the future. At the end of each work day and at the end of construction at each culvert, the coffer dams will be removed, and full tidal function will be restored to the work area.

Before work starts, a Service-approved biologist lead will start from the center of the work area and move outward to flush any potential species outward. Immediately following those activities, all vegetation within the Action Area, and within a 4-foot buffer around the Project Area, will be cut to no more than two inches high. Roots of native vegetation will be left for regeneration. This includes vegetation on the banks and within the channel.

All work will take place during the work window of September 1 - January 31, which is outside the California clapper rail breeding season. During extreme high tide events or floods, with an elevation greater than 6.5 feet, construction activities will maintain a 50-foot buffer from clapper rails.

At the end of each day, debris will be removed from the work area and coffer dams will be removed. Work at each culvert will take approximately two to three days, with the total

construction time spanning 12-18 days. All work will occur during low tides (*i.e.*, no work will occur during or immediately after storm events). The Project is expected to last for two construction seasons (winter/spring) starting in 2020. No revegetation monitoring is planned as the tidal marsh ecotone typically rapidly revegetates and develops habitat features similar to the surrounding conditions.

Conservation Measures

The Applicant will implement the following conservation measures to minimize adverse effects of the Project to the salt marsh harvest mouse.

1. Prior to initiating construction a Service-approved biologist will inspect suitable habitat prior to vegetation removal and search for signs of harvest mice. Following inspection, personnel, under the supervision of the biologist, will disturb (*e.g.*, flush) vegetation to encourage movement of salt marsh harvest mouse into adjacent marsh areas. Flushing of vegetation will first occur in the center of the site then progress toward the two upland sides of the culverts. The biologist will sweep the work area and equipment daily before work begins, and will be available on-call for each work day.
2. Vegetation will be removed with hand tools (*e.g.* weed-eater, hoe, rake, trowel, shovel, grazing) so that vegetation is no taller than 2 inches, and will be removed from the Project area plus a four foot buffer at each culvert. No vegetation will remain during the implementation of construction activities. All non-native, invasive vegetation removed will be discarded at a location outside of any tidal marsh areas to prevent reseeding.
3. Construction will not occur within 50 feet of suitable tidal marsh habitat within two hours before and after an extreme high tide event (*i.e.*, 6.5 feet or higher measured at the Golden Gate Bridge and adjusted to the timing of local high tides) or when adjacent marsh is flooded.

The Applicant will implement the following conservation measures to minimize adverse effects of the Project to the California clapper rail:

1. Construction work will occur only during the September 1 to January 31 work window to avoid disturbance to nesting rails.
4. Construction will not occur within 50 feet of suitable tidal marsh habitat within two hours before and after an extreme high tide event (*i.e.*, 6.5 feet or higher measured at the Golden Gate Bridge and adjusted to the timing of local high tides) or when adjacent marsh is flooded.

The Applicant will also implement general best management practices to maintain the environmental conditions and habitat quality at the site for the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail, summarized below.

1. An environmental education program consisting of a brief presentation will cover a description of the focal listed species and their habitat needs, known occurrences of these species near the Project footprint, the legal status of these species, and the various measures being implemented to reduce potential impacts to the species during implementation. Fact sheets conveying this information will be distributed to the personnel that receive the awareness training. A record of personnel that have received the training will be maintained by the Service-approved biologist.
2. Standard construction best management practices shall be employed to limit erosion and protect water quality including prohibiting storage of hazardous materials, such as materials used as fuel and for equipment maintenance, where they could affect wildlife habitat or enter waters draining to the San Francisco Bay. The Applicant will prepare and implement a spill prevention and control plan to minimize the potential for spills of hazardous materials. Spill kits will be present for any work adjacent to open waters, and will contain oil booms of sufficient length to surround excavation equipment working near these waters. All spills of oil and other hazardous materials will be immediately contained and cleaned up. Any hazardous materials cleaned up or used on-site will be properly disposed of at an approved disposal facility.
3. Any equipment used during the Action shall be maintained to be free of leaks. Heavy equipment shall only be operated or staged in areas previously cleared of vegetation. Staging/storage areas for equipment, materials, fuels, lubricants, and solvents, shall be located outside of the tidal marsh and associated riparian area. Stationary equipment such as motors, pumps, and compressors located adjacent to the waterway, shall be positioned over drip-pans.
4. During all activities at the project site, all construction trash that may attract predators shall be properly contained, removed from the work site, and disposed of regularly. Following maintenance activities, all construction trash and maintenance debris shall be removed from work sites and disposed of properly.
5. All exposed or disturbed areas on the road shoulder shall be covered with seed-free rice straw to reduce erosion.
6. The Applicant will ensure that the spread or introduction of invasive exotic plants shall be avoided to the maximum extent possible. When practicable, invasive exotic plants at the work site shall be removed. In order to deter the spread of the pathogen that causes sudden oak death, when leaving China Camp State Park, staff/contractors will wash mud or soil from all equipment and protective clothing.

Action Area

The Action Area is defined in 50 CFR § 402.02, as “all areas to be affected directly or indirectly by the Federal action and not merely the immediate area involved in the action.” The Action Area for this consultation encompasses all areas that may be directly or indirectly affected as a result of activities for the Project and the broader area that, while outside the Project footprint,

may be directly or indirectly affected by vibrations, noise, dust, light, or movement associated with the proposed Project.

The Applicant has an access easement on North San Pedro Road, as well as the road shoulder extending 25 feet from the centerline of the asphalt on either side of the road. The Action Area includes the Project footprint (0.05 acre of existing tidal marsh at the termini of each culvert, and 0.01 acre of culvert, headwall, and road shoulder) as well as 30.00 acres of valley grassland/oak woodland, 10.29 acres of oak woodland, 6.91 acres of willow scrub/wetland sedge meadow, 4.20 acres of paved road, and 1.43 acres of wetland sedge meadow.

Analytical Framework for the Jeopardy Determination

Section 7(a)(2) of the Act requires that Federal agencies ensure that any action they authorize, fund, or carry out is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species. “Jeopardize the continued existence of” means to engage in an action that reasonably will be expected, directly or indirectly, to reduce appreciably the likelihood of both the survival and recovery of a listed species in the wild by reducing the reproduction, numbers, or distribution of that species (50 CFR § 402.02).

The jeopardy analysis in this biological opinion considers the effects of the proposed Federal action, and any cumulative effects, on the rangewide survival and recovery of the listed species. It relies on four components: (1) the *Status of the Species*, which describes the current rangewide condition of the species, the factors responsible for that condition, and its survival and recovery needs; (2) the *Environmental Baseline*, which analyzes the current condition of the species in the Action Area without the consequences to the listed species caused by the proposed action, the factors responsible for that condition, and the relationship of the Action Area to the survival and recovery of the species; (3) the *Effects of the Action*, which includes all effects that are caused by the proposed Federal action; and (4) the *Cumulative Effects*, which evaluates the effects of future, non-Federal activities in the Action Area on the species. The *Effects of the Action* and *Cumulative Effects* are added to the *Environmental Baseline* and in light of the *Status of the Species*, the Service formulates its opinion as to whether the proposed action is likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species.

Status of Species

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

There are two subspecies of the salt marsh harvest mouse: the northern subspecies (*R. r. halicoetes*) and the southern subspecies (*R. r. raviventris*) both of which are listed as endangered. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species’ range-wide status, please refer to the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California*, available at: www.fws.gov/sfbaydelta/documents/tidal_marsh_recovery_plan_v1.pdf (Service 2013b). Critical habitat has not been designated for this species. Threats evaluated during the drafting of the recovery plan and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species since its publication, with loss of habitat being the most significant effect. While there have been continued losses of salt marsh harvest mouse habitat throughout the various recovery units,

including the San Pablo Bay Recovery Unit where the proposed project is located, to date no project has proposed a level of effects for which the Service has issued a biological opinion determining jeopardy for the species. The Service is in the process of developing our current 5-year review for the species. The salt marsh harvest mouse is a Fully Protected Species under California law (California Fish and Game Code §3511).

California Clapper Rail

The California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*) was federally listed as endangered in 1970 (Service 1970). Critical habitat has not been proposed or designated. A five-year review was completed in 2013 (Service 2013a). This subspecies is one of three in California listed as endangered under the Endangered Species Act (Act). The other subspecies are the light-footed clapper rail (*R. l. levipes*), which is found in tidal marshes in southern California and northwestern Baja California, and the Yuma clapper rail (*R. l. yumanensis*), which is restricted to the Colorado River Basin. A detailed account of the taxonomy, ecology, and biology of the California clapper rail can be found in the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California* (Service 2013b). The California clapper rail is a Fully Protected Species under California law (California Fish and Game Code §3511).

Historically, the California clapper rail was abundant in all tidal salt and brackish marshes in the San Francisco Bay vicinity, as well as in all of the larger tidal estuaries from Marin to San Luis Obispo counties. Current distribution is restricted almost entirely to the marshes of the Bay Area and where the only known breeding populations occur. California clapper rail population numbers have generally fluctuated over time and have never improved to a level warranting consideration for downlisting the status of the species since its original listing as endangered in 1970. Citing various sources, the 2013 five-year review of the California clapper rail reported a population estimated at 4,200 to 6,000 birds between 1971-1975, at only 1,500 birds between 1981-1987, and reaching an estimated all-time historical low of about 500 birds in 1991. The five-year review noted that California clapper rail numbers have rebounded slightly since the early 1990s, but that substantial increases in population may be difficult to achieve due to the current disjunct distribution of their habitat (Service 2013a).

The Invasive *Spartina* Project (ISP), a multi-partner, regional non-native *Spartina* control program, conducts annual San Francisco Bay Estuary-wide California clapper rail surveys at program-associated sites. Annual ISP California clapper rail surveys at 30 sites across the estuary from 2005-2010 showed an increase from 80 birds in 2005, to 140 birds in 2007, before declining to below 60 birds in 2010 (McBroom *et al.* 2011). The ISP has expanded the number of sites included in its rail surveys, and for 158 sites across the estuary from 2010-2015, the project reported fluctuating numbers with 577 rails in 2010, a low of 498 in 2013, and a rebound to 670 birds in 2015 (McBroom 2015).

Throughout their distribution, California clapper rails occur within a range of tidal and brackish marshes (Harvey *et al.* 1977). Rail foraging and refugial habitat encompasses the lower, middle, and high marsh zones, as well as the adjacent transitional zone. In south and central San Francisco Bay, and along the perimeter of San Pablo Bay, rails typically inhabit tidal marshes dominated by *Sarcocornia pacifica* and *Spartina foliosa*, especially where significant high tide

refugia exist. In the North Bay, clapper rails also occur in tidal brackish marshes that vary significantly in vegetation structure and composition, ranging from salt-brackish marsh to fresh-brackish marsh transitions. Breeding California clapper rails occur almost exclusively in tidal salt and brackish marshes with unrestricted daily tidal flows, adequate invertebrate prey food supply, well developed tidal channel networks, and suitable nesting and escape cover for refuge during extreme tides. They exhibit strong site fidelity and territorial defense and are considered sensitive to disturbance. They tend to have relatively small average home ranges of 4.7 hectares (11.6 acres) and core use areas of 0.9 hectares (2.2 acres). Threats to the species include, but are not limited to, habitat destruction and modification, low adult survivorship (ranging from 0.49 to 0.52), and predation of adults and eggs/nestlings (Service 2013b).

Environmental Baseline

Environmental Baseline refers to the condition of the listed species or its designated critical habitat in the Action Area, without the consequences to the listed species or designated critical habitat caused by the proposed action. The Environmental Baseline includes the past and present impacts of all Federal, State, or private actions and other human activities in the Action Area, the anticipated impacts of all proposed Federal projects in the Action Area that have already undergone formal or early section 7 consultation, and the impact of State or private actions which are contemporaneous with the consultation in process. The consequences to listed species or designated critical habitat from ongoing agency activities or existing agency facilities that are not within the agency's discretion to modify are part of the *Environmental Baseline*.

Surrounding Land Use

The Action Area is located in the North Bay region of the San Francisco Bay on 403- and 304-acre parcels owned by the Applicant. The six culverts to be rehabilitated are located under North San Pedro Road where the road runs along the edge of San Pablo Bay. This portion of the road runs through China Camp State Park; a campground and other Park facilities are located within 1,000 feet of mile markers 3.25 – 3.39, but the area is generally undeveloped open space. Two of the culverts (3.25 and 3.81) drain upland ephemeral freshwater streams via the marsh to the Bay; they and the other four culverts pass salt water back and forth with the tides.

Vegetation in China Camp is a diverse mix of wetland and upland habitats and includes existing tidal marsh, valley grassland/oak woodland, oak woodland, willow scrub/wetland sedge meadow, and wetland sedge meadow. Tidal marsh extends out from both sides of the road. *Spartina foliosa*, pickleweed, alkali heath, jaumea, gum plant, salt grass, and other common marsh plant species are present. All of the marsh habitat that surrounds the Project Area is already under State ownership, and is protected as a state park.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

Potential nesting/breeding habitat for salt marsh harvest mouse is present in tidal marsh areas within and adjacent to the Action Area. Trapping performed by the California Department of Fish and Wildlife (CDFW) in 2014 confirmed the species was present in the brackish muted tidal marsh habitat on the south side of North San Pedro Road (within the Action Area) in Miwok

Meadows and Back Ranch Meadows (CDFW 2015). No substantial changes in habitat have occurred since that time, and therefore salt marsh harvest mouse is presumed to be extant in the marshes surrounding and within the Action Area, on both sides of North San Pedro Road. Salt marsh harvest mice may also occasionally venture some distance into the valley grasslands and freshwater wetlands within the Action Area to exploit foraging opportunities, though such use is anticipated to be restricted to the nocturnal period.

California Clapper Rail

The tidal marsh habitat surrounding the Action Area has been surveyed annually in recent years for the presence of California clapper rail by the Invasive Spartina Project and Point Blue Conservation Science (PBCS); both organizations have detected numerous California clapper rails during breeding season surveys in the surrounding marshes (PBCS 2014; McBroom 2017). California clapper rails presumably have the potential to nest in suitable tidal and muted tidal marsh habitat throughout the Action Area. They are also likely to forage in the tidal channels that flow into and out of the culverts during low tide periods.

Effects of the Action

Effects of the Action are all consequences to listed species or critical habitat that are caused by the proposed action, including the consequences of other activities that are caused by the proposed action. A consequence is caused by the proposed action if it would not occur but for the proposed action and it is reasonably certain to occur. Effects of the Action may occur later in time and may include consequences occurring outside the immediate area involved in the action.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

Salt marsh harvest mouse has been documented in brackish muted tidal marsh habitat in the southwestern portion of the Action Area buffers, and the species is presumed to be extant in surrounding tidal marshes. There is also potential for salt marsh harvest mouse to make short-term movements into the valley grassland and freshwater wetlands to forage, though this is anticipated to occur largely at night, outside of daily construction windows.

The Action will result in the temporary loss of 0.03 acre of existing tidal marsh habitat on the northeast side of North San Pedro Road, and 0.02 acre of brackish muted tidal marsh on the southwest side of the road (through removal of vegetation that will recolonize). There will be permanent improvements to the culverts that link salt marsh harvest mouse habitat on either side of the road, which will restore freshwater flows, increase the range of flows through the culverts, and potentially provide movement corridors for salt marsh harvest mouse.

Potential effects to salt marsh harvest mouse include temporary habitat loss; temporary displacement, disturbance and interruption of behavioral processes; and injury or mortality of adults, young and nests. Habitat loss will occur through vegetation clearing for salt marsh harvest

mouse exclusion, and could lead to an increased risk of predation through reduced cover, though this effect will be temporary. Disturbance and interruption of behavioral processes (*e.g.*, feeding, breeding), could result from the presence of workers and use of equipment near marsh habitats causing visual, audible, and vibratory disruption. The Applicant estimates visual, audible, and vibratory disturbances could occur in habitat during construction activities within 2,200 and 3,500 feet of the construction activities from operating (simultaneously or independently) an excavator or vectoring truck, using a formula to determine the distance of Project related noise (*i.e.*, the distance sound would attenuate to ambient sound level by incorporating the distance from noise source, reference measurement distance, and reduction over distance).

If any mice are present during the vegetation removal activities, active flushing would likely result in similar disturbance and interruption of normal behavioral processes. Injury and mortality of adults, juveniles, and nestlings could occur during vegetation removal, during construction activities associated with the culvert repairs (*e.g.*, sandbag placement), and through placement of material during repair of the shoulder, but only if salt marsh harvest mouse actively move into the work area after it has been cleared by the approved biologist. All of these effects can lead to reduced fitness for individuals.

The primary goal of the Project is to repair six culverts linking salt marsh harvest mouse habitat on either side of North San Pedro Road, and overall effects to salt marsh harvest mouse are anticipated to be beneficial, enhancing the quality of marsh habitat in the Action Area. The Action will also result in repairs to the shoulder of the road, which can serve as high tide refuge for salt marsh harvest mouse, but which could also facilitate higher rates of public access. However, the Park is already subject to high levels of public use, so any potential increases in use (and potential disturbance) are likely to be negligible.

California Clapper Rail

Breeding populations of California clapper rail are known to be present in the marshes of China Camp State Park. It is unlikely, however, that California clapper rail nest within the limited tidal habitat within the Project Area due to the limited habitat availability, but it is presumed that nesting may occur within 200 meters of Project Area within adjacent, suitable muted and fully tidal marsh. The Project will result in the temporary loss of 0.03 acre of existing tidal marsh habitat on the northeast side of North San Pedro Road, and 0.02 acre of brackish muted tidal marsh on the southwest side of the road (through removal of vegetation that will recolonize).

There will be potential improvements to habitat via increased vegetative cover where the shoulders are rebuilt, potentially leading to an increased prey base. There will be permanent improvements to the culverts that link California clapper rail habitat on either side of the road, which will restore freshwater flows, increase the range of tidal flows through the culverts, and potentially provide movement corridors for California clapper rail.

Potential effects to California clapper rail include temporary habitat loss and displacement; disturbance and interruption of behavioral processes; and, injury or mortality of adults and/or

young. Temporary habitat loss will occur through vegetation clearing (for salt marsh harvest mouse exclusion), and could lead to increased risk of predation on California clapper rail through reduced cover, though any latter such effects are expected to be minimal due to the relatively small area of tidal wetland impacted within the context of the surrounding environment.

There is a limited potential for the disturbance of a small number of (non-nesting) California clapper rails if birds are foraging within the Action Area. Injury and mortality of adults could occur during vegetation removal, during construction activities associated with the culvert repairs (e.g., sandbag placement), and through placement of material during repair of the shoulder, but only if California clapper rail actively move into the work area after it has been cleared by the approved biologist. All of these effects can lead to reduced fitness for individuals.

The primary goal of the Project is to repair six culverts linking California clapper rail habitat on either side of North San Pedro Road, and overall effects to California clapper rail are anticipated to be beneficial, enhancing the quality marsh habitat in the Action Area. The Action will also result in repairs to the shoulder of the road, which can serve as high tide refuge for California clapper rail, but which could also facilitate higher rates of public access. However, the Park is already subject to high levels of public use, so any potential increases in use (and potential disturbance) are likely to be negligible.

Adult California clapper rail and nests could be physically injured or killed, or nests could be abandoned during construction activities. To eliminate this risk, no work will occur during the rail nesting season, all potential vegetative habitat (tidal marsh within the Project footprint plus a four foot buffer) will be removed using prescribed methods before any construction activities occur at each culvert, and no work will take place during extremely high tides when California clapper rail are highly dependent on cover to avoid predation.

Vegetation removal for salt marsh harvest mouse exclusion will result in the temporary loss of a relatively small amount of tidal marsh habitat, though vegetation is expected to regenerate quickly. California clapper rail may be negatively impacted by visual, audible, and vibratory disturbances from operating (simultaneously or independently) an excavator or vectoring truck, using a formula to determine the distance of Project related noise (i.e., the distance sound would attenuate to ambient sound level by incorporating the distance from noise source, reference measurement distance, and reduction over distance) in habitat during construction activities within 2,200 and 3,500 feet of the construction activities. However, a monitor will be on site during any work in and directly adjacent to potential California clapper rail habitat and will stop all work if a rail is observed in the area, until the animal leaves on its own. These measures will prevent injury and mortality to California clapper rails and will minimize disturbance. Ultimately the Project will result in improved linkages between California clapper rail habitat on either side of North San Pedro Road and improvement of the road shoulder, which can serve as high tide refuge for California clapper rails, and is therefore anticipated to have an overall beneficial effect on California clapper rails.

Cumulative Effects

Cumulative Effects include the effects of future State, Tribal, local or private actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area considered in this biological opinion. Future Federal actions unrelated to the proposed Project are not considered in this section, because they require separate consultation pursuant to section 7 of the Act. During this consultation, the Service did not identify any future non-Federal actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area of the proposed Project.

Conclusion

After reviewing the current *Status of the Species* for salt marsh harvest mouse, the *Environmental Baseline* for the Action Area, the *Effects of the Action*, and the *Cumulative Effects*, it is the Service's biological opinion that the proposed Project is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the salt marsh harvest mouse or California clapper rail. The Service reached this conclusion because the project-related effects to the species, when added to the environmental baseline and analyzed in consideration of all potential cumulative effects, will not rise to the level of reducing the likelihood of survival or recovery of the species based on the following: (1) significant mortality or reduction in the population size is not anticipated to result from the proposed Project; (2) the habitat affected by the proposed Project will not be permanently altered, fragmented, or reduced in foraging and sheltering quality to the extent the population of salt marsh harvest mice or California clapper rails in the area are at risk of extirpation; and (3) the Project will benefit the on-site population of salt marsh harvest mice and California clapper rails by virtue of producing higher connectivity of habitat vegetation on either side of North San Pedro Road.

INCIDENTAL TAKE STATEMENT

Section 9 of the Act and Federal regulation pursuant to section 4(d) of the Act prohibit the take of endangered and threatened species, respectively, without special exemption. Take is defined as to harass, harm, pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture or collect, or to attempt to engage in any such conduct. Harass is defined by Service regulations at 50 CFR § 17.3 as an intentional or negligent act or omission which creates the likelihood of injury to a listed species by annoying it to such an extent as to significantly disrupt normal behavioral patterns which include, but are not limited to, breeding, feeding or sheltering. Harm is defined by the same regulations as an act which actually kills or injures wildlife. Harm is further defined to include significant habitat modification or degradation that results in death or injury to listed species by significantly impairing essential behavioral patterns including breeding, feeding, or sheltering. Incidental take is defined as take that is incidental to, and not the purpose of, the carrying out of an otherwise lawful activity. Under the terms of section 7(b)(4) and section 7(o)(2), taking incidental to and not intended as part of the agency action is not considered to be prohibited taking under the Act, provided that such taking is in compliance with the terms and conditions of this Incidental Take Statement.

The measures described below are non-discretionary, and must be undertaken by the Corps so that they become binding conditions of any grant or permit issued to the Applicants, as appropriate, for the exemption in section 7(o)(2) to apply. The Corps has a continuing duty to regulate the activity covered by this incidental take statement. If the Corps (1) fails to assume and implement the terms and conditions, or (2) fails to require the (Applicants) to adhere to the terms and conditions of the incidental take statement through enforceable terms that are added to the permit or grant document, the protective coverage of section 7(o)(2) may lapse. In order to monitor the impact of incidental take, the Corps must report the progress of the action and its impact on the species to the Service as specified in the incidental take statement [50 CFR § 402.14(i)(3)].

Amount or Extent of Take

The Service anticipates incidental take of the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail will be difficult to detect or quantify for the following reasons: the inherently elusive behavior, propensity to move rapidly through vegetation, and their cryptic occupancy of vegetation types resulting in low detectability. There is a risk of injury or mortality as a result of the proposed activities and subsequent temporary loss or degradation of suitable habitat. Therefore, the Service anticipates take incidental to the proposed action in the form of harm, including injury or mortality, and impairing the essential behaviors of all salt marsh harvest mice and California clapper rails within the:

- 1) 0.03 acre of existing tidal marsh habitat on the northeast side of North San Pedro Road resulting from active flushing of salt marsh harvest mouse and temporary habitat loss of both species during vegetation clearing,
- 2) 0.02 acre of brackish muted tidal marsh on the southwest side of North San Pedro Road resulting from active flushing of salt marsh harvest mouse and temporary habitat loss of both species during vegetation clearing, and
- 3) in the adjacent salt marsh habitat within 3,500 feet of construction due to the temporary sound impacts of Project implementation.

Upon implementation of the following reasonable and prudent measures, incidental take of salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rails associated with the Project will become exempt from the prohibitions described in section 9 of the Act. No other forms of take are exempted under this opinion.

Effect of the Take

In the accompanying biological opinion, the Service determined that the level of anticipated take is not likely to jeopardize the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail.

Reasonable and Prudent Measure

All necessary and appropriate measures to avoid or minimize effects on the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail resulting from implementation of this Project have been incorporated into the Project's proposed *Conservation Measures*. Therefore, the Service believes the following reasonable and prudent measure is necessary and appropriate to minimize the incidental take of the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail:

- 1) All *Conservation Measures*, as described in the BA and restated in the *Description of the Proposed Action* section of this biological opinion, shall be fully implemented and adhered to. Further, this reasonable and prudent measure shall be supplemented by the Term and Condition below.

Terms and Conditions

In order to be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of the Act, the Corps shall ensure compliance with the following term and condition, which implement the reasonable and prudent measure described above. This Term and Condition is non-discretionary.

- 1) Term and Condition 1 implements Reasonable and Prudent Measure 1:
 - A) The Corps shall minimize the potential for harm, killing or other forms of take of the salt marsh harvest mouse from Project-related activities by implementation of the *Conservation Measures* proposed in the Description of the Proposed Action in this biological opinion.
 - B) The Corps shall ensure that the Applicant immediately notifies the Service of any killed, injured, or entrapped salt marsh harvest mice or California clapper rails, within one (1) working day of the detection. Please contact the Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Division at: San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office, 650 Capitol Mall, Suite 8-300, Sacramento, California 95814 or by telephone at (916) 930-2664.
 - C) The Corps and/or Applicant shall educate and inform personnel involved in the Project as to the *Conservation Measures* and Terms and Conditions in this biological opinion.
 - D) The Corps shall comply with the reporting requirements of this biological opinion, including a post-construction report outlining how the *Conservation Measures* were implemented for this Project.
 - E) The Corps and/or Applicant shall ensure any personnel identified as biological monitors or biologists, who are responsible for ensuring compliance with the *Conservation Measures* or other parts of the Project which may affect federally-listed species, be Service-approved prior to implementing those activities.

Reporting Requirements

In order to monitor whether the amount or extent of incidental take anticipated from implementation of the Project is approached or exceeded, the Corps shall adhere to the following reporting requirements. Should this anticipated amount or extent of incidental take be exceeded, the Corps must reinitiate formal consultation as per 50 CFR § 402.16.

- 1) The Service must be notified within 24 hours of the finding of any injured or dead listed species or any unanticipated damage to its habitat associated with the proposed Project. Injured listed species shall be cared by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person, such as the Service-approved biologist for the proposed Project. Notification will be made to the contact above in Term and Condition 1B, and must include the date, time, and precise location of the individual/incident clearly indicated on a U.S. Geological Survey 7.5 minute quadrangle or other maps at a finer scale, as requested by the Service, and any other pertinent information. When an injured or dead individual of the listed species is found, the Corps shall follow the steps outlined in the Salvage and Disposition of Individuals Taken section below.
- 2) Sightings of any listed or sensitive animal species shall be reported to the Service and the California Natural Diversity Data Base (<https://www.wildlife.ca.gov/Data/CNDDDB/Submitting-Data>).
- 3) The Applicant shall submit a post-construction compliance report prepared by the on-site biologist to the San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office within 60 calendar days of the date of the completion of construction activities. This report shall detail (i) dates that construction occurred; (ii) pertinent information concerning the success of the Project in meeting the avoidance and minimization measures; (iii) an explanation of failure to meet such measures, if any; (iv) known Project effects on the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail, if any; (v) occurrences of incidental take of these listed species, if any; (vi) documentation of employee environmental education; and (vii) other pertinent information.

Salvage and Disposition of Individuals

Injured listed species must be cared for by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person(s), such as the Service-approved biologist. Dead individuals must be sealed in a resealable plastic bag containing a paper with the date and time when the animal was found, the location where it was found, and the name of the person who found it, and the bag containing the specimen frozen in a freezer located in a secure site, until instructions are received from the Service regarding the disposition of the dead specimen. The Service contact persons are the Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Division at (916) 930-2664; and the Resident Agent-in-Charge of the Service's Office of Law Enforcement, 5622 Price Way, McClellan, California 95562, at (916) 569-8444.

CONSERVATION RECOMMENDATIONS

Section 7(a)(1) of the Act directs Federal agencies to utilize their authorities to further the purposes of the Act by carrying out conservation programs for the benefit of endangered and threatened species. Conservation recommendations are discretionary agency activities to minimize or avoid adverse effects of a proposed action on listed species or critical habitat, to help implement recovery plans, or to develop information. The Service recommends the following actions:

- 1) Encourage or require the use of appropriate California native species in restoration efforts.
- 2) Facilitate additional educational programs geared toward the importance and conservation of tidal marsh and seasonal wetlands.
- 3) Assist the Service with implementing other recovery actions identified within the most current recovery plans for salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail.
- 4) Encourage the participation of the Applicant in programs being developed by the Federal and State resource agencies to limit and reverse the spread of non-natives, such as *Phragmites*, *Lepidium*, clams, and other invasives within Suisun Marsh.

In order for the Service to be kept informed of actions minimizing or avoiding adverse effects or benefiting listed species or their habitats, the Service requests notification of the implementation of any conservation recommendations.

REINITIATION – CLOSING STATEMENT

This concludes consultation for the Marin County Department of Public Works North San Pedro Road Culvert Rehabilitation Project. As provided in 50 CFR § 402.16,

- 1) Reinitiation of formal consultation is required and shall be requested by the Federal agency or by the Service where discretionary Federal agency involvement or control over the action has been retained or is authorized by law and:
 - A) If the amount or extent of taking specified in the incidental take statement is exceeded;
 - B) If new information reveals effects of the action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not previously considered;
 - C) If the identified action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat that was not considered in the biological opinion;
or

- D) If a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the identified action.
- 2) An agency shall not be required to reinitiate consultation after the approval of a land management plan prepared pursuant to 43 U.S.C. 1712 or 16 U.S.C. 1604 upon listing of a new species or designation of new critical habitat if the land management plan has been adopted by the agency as of the date of listing or designation, provided that any authorized actions that may affect the newly listed species or designated critical habitat will be addressed through a separate action-specific consultation. This exception to reinitiation of consultation shall not apply to those land management plans prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604 if:
 - A) Fifteen years have passed since the date the agency adopted the land management plan prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604; and
 - B) Five years have passed since the enactment of Public Law 115-141 [March 23, 2018] or the date of the listing of a species or the designation of critical habitat, whichever is later.

Please address any question or concern regarding this response by contacting Elden Holldorf, Fish and Wildlife Biologist by telephone at 916-930-5614 or via email at Elden_Holldorf@fws.gov or Kim Squires, Section 7 Division Chief, via email at Kim_Squires@fws.gov. Please refer to the Service File Number: 08FBDT00-2019-F-0056 in any future correspondence regarding this Project.

Sincerely,

Kaylee Allen
Field Supervisor

cc: Ms. Roberta Morganstern, U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, San Francisco, California
Ms. Laurie Williams, Marin County Department of Public Works, San Rafael, California

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